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Calibration of the SMAP soil moisture retrieval algorithm to reduce bias over the Amazon rainforest

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Abstract— Soil moisture (SM) is crucial for the Earth's ecosystem, impacting climate and vegetation health. Obtaining in-situ observations of SM is labor-intensive and complex, particularly in remote and densely vegetated regions like the Amazon rainforest. NASA's Soil Moisture Active and Passive (SMAP) mission, utilizing an L-band radiometer, aims to monitor global SM . While it has been validated in areas with low Vegetation Water Content (VWC) ($< 5 \text{ kg/m}^2$), its efficiency in the Amazon, which has dense canopies and high VWC ($> 10 \text{ kg/m}^2$), is uncertain due to scarce in-situ measurements. This study validates and analyzes SMAP data in the Amazon, employing the single-channel algorithm (SCA) and adjusting vegetation optical depth (τ) and single scattering albedo (ω), two key vegetation parameters. It incorporates *in-situ* SM observations from three old-growth rainforest locations: Tambopata (Southwest Amazon), Manaus (Central Amazon), and Caxiuaña (Eastern Amazon). There were substantial discrepancies between SMAP and in-situ data. However, using calibrated τ and ω values, characterized by a lower τ , results in better agreement with in-situ measurements. The study emphasizes the pressing need for innovative methodologies to accurately assess SM in high VWC regions like the Amazon using SMAP data.

Index Terms—Remote sensing, soil moisture, Vegetation optical depth, Amazon rainforest, Soil Moisture Active/Passive (SMAP)

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I. INTRODUCTION

Soil moisture (SM) is a key component of water and energy cycles [1], [2], [3], [4] affecting evapotranspiration, infiltration, and runoff [1], [2], [5]. SM is also a vital source of water, supporting ecosystem function and productivity [6], [7]. Precise estimation and consistent monitoring of SM are paramount to comprehending climate change and its subsequent ramifications on the ecosystem, particularly during extended periods of drought [8], [9].

In situ observations of SM are significantly laborious and have the capacity to offer observations on a comparatively small scale [10]. In remote areas these measurements are sparse. To overcome these limitations, satellite observations of SM has been devised as a compelling alternative to *in situ* observations. Satellites, utilizing optical, thermal, and microwave signals, are proficient in ceaselessly observing the spatial distributions of SM [11].

The Soil Moisture Active and Passive (SMAP) mission [12] is focused on measuring global SM through the employment of an L-band (1.41 GHz) microwave radiometer. The National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA) launched the SMAP satellite in January 2015, its primary goal being the observation of global SM and the freeze-thaw state of soil, utilizing both active and passive microwave sensors. However, after the malfunction of the active sensor, since July 2015, SMAP has been reliant solely on its passive sensor for the collection of SM data. Passive microwave remote sensing at low frequency can provide global SM at a high temporal resolution, with minimal interference from weather conditions and surface roughness. SMAP provides SM data retrieved through algorithms predicated on the correlation between the soil dielectric constant and SM [13], [14], [15]. SMAP SM retrieval algorithms include the single channel algorithm (SCA) and the dual channel algorithm (DCA). These algorithms utilize vertically polarized brightness temperature (T_{BV}) and horizontally polarized brightness temperatures (T_{BH}) as their input parameters. The suite of available SMAP products includes Level 2 (half-orbit, with a resolution of 36 km) and Level 3 (daily composite, with a resolution of 36 km), both capturing the top 5 cm depth of SM . Each level of data also includes Enhanced products, which provide improved quality and a more granular 9 km spatial resolution. All SMAP

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offerings incorporate SM data retrieved from both the T_{BV} -based single channel algorithm (SCA-V), the T_{BH} -based single channel algorithm (SCA-H), and the dual channel algorithm (DCA). DCA has emerged as the standard baseline algorithm for SMAP [16].

The accuracy of the SMAP SM products has been validated against field observations at sites comprising a variety of land cover types. Colliander et al. [17] assessed the performance of the SMAP SM products using data collected from 18 core validation sites. The results confirmed that SMAP radiometer-based SM data products exhibit high fidelity (with an unbiased root mean squared difference (ubRMSD) less than $0.04 \text{ m}^3/\text{m}^3$) in areas with a vegetation water content (VWC) below $5 \text{ kg}/\text{m}^2$. Ayres et al. [18] conducted SMAP SM data validation against the *in situ* SM observations collected from 40 National Ecological Observatory Network (NEON) sites, which included 19 forest locations. The SMAP SM data were shown to be reliable over unforested regions (ubRMSD $0.046 \text{ m}^3/\text{m}^3$; the spatial representativeness errors inflate the ubRMSD values compared to the core sites), while the SMAP SM data over forested regions are less accurate (ubRMSD $0.053 - 0.06 \text{ m}^3/\text{m}^3$). Other validation studies emphasized reconsidering physical temperature, vegetation transmission, and scattering parameters in SM retrieval for forest-covered regions [19]. The SMAP SM data overall has been confirmed to possess commendable quality for non-forested regions, but it requires further enhancements for densely forested regions with VWC within the range of $6-18 \text{ kg}/\text{m}^2$ [20]. Notably, the Amazon rainforest, with its high and dense tree coverage [21], [22], has a VWC approximately around $15 \text{ kg}/\text{m}^2$ [20].

Efforts to improve SM retrieval have been numerous and noteworthy. For instance, Konings et al. [23] introduced the multi-temporal DCA (MT-DCA), which retrieves SM , vegetation optical depth (VOD), and effective scattering albedo. The MT-DCA led to a reduction in ubRMSD ($\sim 0.01 \text{ m}^3/\text{m}^3$) of SM retrievals when compared to the SCA-V, barring tropical forests and agriculture regions. Chaubell et al. [24], [25] further refined the DCA implementation for the SMAP SM product, outperforming SCA-V [17]. Recently, Li et al. [26] introduced SMAP-INRAE-BORDEAUX (SMAP-IB), built on the L-band Microwave Emission of the Biosphere model (L-MEB). Their findings suggests that SMAP-IB can simulate global SM with similar performance to SCA-V and better performance than MT-DCA and DCA at 36 km resolution. However, performance of SMAP-IB appears to be less satisfactory than SCA-V for areas covered by shrublands, woody savannas, croplands, and cropland/natural mosaics.

The diminished performance of SMAP in areas of dense vegetation can be ascribed to an inadequate reflection of vegetation cover interference in microwave remote sensing. Mitigating this issue necessitates precise estimation of the impact of vegetation on microwave-based remote sensing, which in turn calls for accurate determination of radiative transfer model variables such as VWC and VOD [23], [27]. The SMAP SCA employs VWC derived from Normalized

Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI). This approach, while pragmatic, does not capture real-time vegetation seasonality and is susceptible to saturation [20]. The derived VWC is then utilized in a straightforward linear equation to obtain VOD . SMAP DCA simulates VOD using measurements of both T_{BV} and T_{BH} . However high correlation between these brightness temperature (T_B) observations is known to limit the performance of DCA simulating VOD [28], [29]. While several studies have endeavored to assess and improve VOD [23], [25], the lack of *in situ* data for VWC and VOD complicates efforts to evaluate their accuracy.

The Amazon rainforest, the world's largest tropical rainforest, represents 60% of the global tropical forest. These forests play a crucial role in the global water cycle, transpiring massive amounts of water [30] and accounting for nearly 50% of the region's rainfall via evapotranspiration [12], [31]. Despite the critical role of SM in understanding evapotranspiration over the Amazon rainforest [32], [33], [34], logistic difficulties have led to a scarcity of *in situ* SM observations. The dense and tall canopy cover of the Amazon rainforest further complicates microwave remote sensing of SM . Microwaves emanating from the soil surface undergo modulation due to attenuation and scattering within the canopy layer [35]. This interference in the canopy layer significantly affects the clarity and accuracy of the signals received from the soil, complicating the measurement of soil moisture. To date, SMAP SM data over the Amazon rainforest has not been thoroughly analyzed. As the first ever study comparing *in situ* observations of SM in the Amazon and SMAP SM , our objective is to evaluate the accuracy and performance of the SMAP Level-3 Enhanced SM product by optimizing the parameters of the SMAP SCA-V algorithm for areas with dense canopy cover.

II. MATERIAL AND METHODS

A. Study Sites

The three sites selected for this study are located within various climatic zones of the Amazon rainforest (Fig. 1), characterized by dense, old-growth trees that reach heights up to 30 meters. The first site, Tambopata (12.831°S , 69.283°W), is located within the Tambopata National Forests of Peru, adjacent to the Tambopata River. This region undergoes a dry season spanning 4 to 5 months, commencing in May, with an annual mean temperature of 26°C and a mean annual rainfall (MAR) that fluctuates between 1600 and 2400 mm. Lopez-Gonzalez et al. [36] reports a tree density of 556 trees per hectare in this area, with a basal area of 25.9 square meters per hectare. Data from *in situ* SM measurements have been available from this site on a half-hourly basis since November 2020, utilizing a SM sensor that is installed at a depth of 5 cm within the soil layer. In 2022, this profile was extended to a depth of 1 meter, starting at 5 cm depth. The second site, Manaus (2.609°S , 60.209°W), is located approximately 53 km north of the city of Manaus in Amazonas State, Brazil. This area endures a dry season lasting three months, typically starting in July, with an annual mean temperature similar to

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Tambopata at 26°C and MAR is 2200 mm. Basal area of

Manaus is 29 square meters per hectare [37]. Half-hourly SM data for the Manaus site have been accessible since September 2018 [34]. SM sensors are installed at 13 different depths ranging from 0.025 to 14.3 m. The third site, Caxiuana (1.708°S, 51.529°W), is situated within the Caxiuana National Forest, approximately 350 km west of the city of Belem in Para State, Brazil. The Caxiuana site experiences a dry season lasting four months, typically commencing in August, with an MAR of 2000 mm. The aboveground dry biomass in this area is estimated to be around 200 cubic meters per hectare, while the basal area varies between 30 and 35 square meters per hectare [37]. At this site, half-hourly SM data have been recorded at multiple depths ranging from 10 to 100 cm since 2016. These three sites are dispersed throughout the central, southeastern, and western regions (Fig. 1).

B. SMAP Level 3 Enhanced product

The SMAP Level-3 Enhanced dataset (SPL3SMP_E, Version 5), integral to this study, can be obtained from the National Snow and Ice Data Center (NSIDC). The SMAP satellite operates with a 40° incident angle from the nadir and traverses the equator at Local Solar Time (LST) 6 AM (descending) and 6 PM (ascending), thus enveloping the globe every 2-3 days. The SMAP Level-3 Enhanced product have a spatial resolution of 33 km, which is projected onto a 9 km by 9 km Equal-Area Scalable Earth-2 (EASE2) grid [38]. The SMAP L-Band radiometer measures antenna temperature, which subsequently gets converted to T_B and gridded on the EASE2 grid using the Backus-Gilbert optimal interpolation technique. The SMAP Level-3 Enhanced product is essentially a daily composite of the SMAP Level-2 SM product. In addition to providing SCA SM retrievals from both T_{BV} and T_{BH} , the SMAP Level-3 product also furnishes ancillary data, including NASA Goddard Modeling Assimilation Office (GMAO) GEOS-FP model effective surface temperature [16].

For this study, T_B measured at 6 AM LST was used, which is the primary overpass time typically employed in the validation of SMAP SM products [17]. This time was specifically chosen because the thermal gradient of the soil-vegetation continuum is generally smaller at 6 AM than at 6 PM [39]. The T_{BV} -based SM retrievals exhibit a higher quality than their T_{BH} counterparts [17], [40]. Consequently, this study leveraged only T_{BV} and SM retrieved via SMAP SCA-V. The SMAP Level-3 data spans from March 31st, 2015, through to the present day.

To assess SMAP SM at the Tambopata, Manaus, and Caxiuana sites, a comparative analysis was conducted between SMAP SM data and *in situ* SM observations. Since *in situ* observations are at a point scale, SMAP Level-3 Enhanced data, which have the finest grid size (9km) and quality controlled among SMAP SM products, was utilized. Hereinafter, SMAP SM refers to SMAP Level-3 Enhanced soil moisture. The SMAP SM data corresponding to each site was extracted from the 9-km EASE2 grid of the SMAP SM by

aligning with the center coordinate of the grid cell in closest proximity to the site location (Fig. 1).

C. SMAP SM Retrieval Algorithm

The SMAP SM retrieval algorithm uses microwave radiometry to estimate SM by parameterizing the L-band T_B model for the canopy and soil. The SMAP provides three different SM estimates obtained from the SCA-V, SCA-H, and DCA algorithms. Both SCA-V and SCA-H employ T_{BV} and T_{BH} respectively, while DCA utilizes both T_B observations. These differing polarizations result in distinct characteristics in the T_B observations. Specifically, the electric field vector of the T_{BV} is oriented perpendicular to the Earth's surface, rendering it less susceptible to surface roughness. Conversely, in T_{BH} measurements, the electric field vector is aligned parallel to the Earth's surface, which makes these measurements more sensitive to variations in surface roughness. The response of the T_{BV} measurement to geophysical changes in the scene is more stable than that of the T_{BH} [41], [42], and SCA-V SM retrieval performs better than SCA-H [40], [43]. In this study, we employed SCA-V, a forward model using T_{BV} only. The canopy effect of the SMAP SCA approach is based on the τ - ω model, a simplified representation of the radiative transfer equation for the soil-canopy system [44],

$$T_B^{sim} = T_s e \gamma + T_c (1 - \omega)(1 - \gamma)(1 + r \gamma) \quad (1)$$

$$\gamma = \exp(-\tau \sec \theta) \quad (2)$$

where T_B^{sim} is simulated brightness temperature (T_{BV}^{sim} in SCA-V), e is soil emissivity, T_s is the effective soil temperature, T_c is the effective canopy temperature, τ is the vegetation optical depth, ω is the canopy single scattering albedo, r is the soil reflectivity, θ is the SMAP satellite incidence angle (40°) and γ is the transmissivity of the canopy layer. Fig. 2 shows the concept of the τ - ω model.

Equation (1) and (2) are used to obtain soil emissivity e using SMAP T_B observations and ancillary data of T_s , T_c , and τ . τ is estimated from the ancillary VWC as,

$$\tau = b * VWC \quad (3)$$

where b is a vegetation type and microwave frequency dependent coefficient obtained from a look-up table. VWC is estimated from the NDVI data using land cover-based equations [39].

The SMAP SCA retrieves SM through the soil dielectric mixing model. The dielectric constant is resolved from the smooth surface emissivity and the Fresnel equations. The smooth surface emissivity is computed from the rough surface emissivity using a roughness correction parameter h . The rough surface emissivity is obtained using the τ - ω model in (1). The current SMAP SCA implementation uses the Mironov soil dielectric model [45], also known as the Mineralogy-Based Soil Dielectric Model (MBSDM). Mironov's model uses parameters from a large soil database, including frequency of radiometer, observed SM , and clay fraction. The SMAP SCA-V uses observed and simulated T_{BV} (T_{BV}^{obs} and T_{BV}^{sim}) to retrieve SM by minimizing the cost

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function,

$$f(SM) = (T_B^{sim}(SM) - T_B^{obs})^2 \quad (4)$$

where T_B^{sim} is the brightness temperature simulated by (1) and T_B^{obs} is the SMAP brightness temperature observations.

D. Variability of Precipitation and SM

Mutual interaction between SM and precipitation through various physical mechanisms has been highlighted in prior research [1], [46], [47], [48], [49]. These studies support that SM can exert influence on precipitation by affecting evaporation and other surface energy fluxes. Specifically, wetter soil can contribute to higher atmospheric humidity, which in turn leads to increased precipitation. Additionally, the increase in surface albedo resulting from wetter soil can promote moisture convergence, which in turn, contributes to enhanced precipitation. Recently, the remote sensing of SM through SMAP has enabled the demonstration of correlations between SM and precipitation in a global scale. Observations on a global scale reveal a spectrum of correlations that range from strong to weak positive relationships. However, in certain regions, the correlation is observed to range from weak to negative, which can be attributed to the characteristics of the land cover type and the local climatic conditions [48].

To investigate the sensitivity of SMAP SM to seasonal variations in rainfall within the Amazon rainforest, seasonal averages were compared, specifically focusing on the rainy season (December to February, DJF) and the dry season (June to August, JJA), as well as the difference between these averages (DJF-JJA). Monthly precipitation data was obtained from the Global Precipitation Climatology Centre (GPCC), averaged for the period from 2015 to 2019, and presented at a 0.25° grid resolution. This analysis aimed to deepen the understanding of the sensitivity of SMAP SM to variations in precipitation across different seasons in the Amazon rainforest.

E. Sensitivity Test and Parameter Optimization Approach

The purpose of the parameter sensitivity test is to explore the changes of the SCA SM retrieval algorithm to shifts in vegetation parameters and to assess whether these parameters can be optimized specifically for the Amazon rainforest. Vegetation parameters τ and ω from the SCA-V algorithm were selected to assess the retrieval sensitivity. T_B^{sim} in (4) is strongly influenced not only by T_s and T_c , but also the ancillary data of τ and ω . In the SMAP SCA-V algorithm, τ is directly proportional to the VWC with the coefficient (b) that is contingent on the canopy structure, while ω is fixed variable based on the land cover type [40]. The SMAP ancillary data have a constant ω (0.07) across all forest types, and a time-varying τ calculated from (3), for the Amazon rainforest region. Considering the possibility that given SMAP ancillary τ and ω may not accurately represent the dense and tall Amazon rainforest, biases in SMAP SM when compared to in situ observations can be expected. To assess the sensitivity of

the SMAP SM retrievals to τ and ω , a range of values were used. For ω , values within the range of 0.05-0.11, based on the SMAP ancillary data, were used. For τ , the SMAP ancillary value of τ was multiplied by a proportional coefficient ranging from 100% (1x) to 50% (0.5x). The ranges of τ and ω align with those found in literature [23], [24]. The sensitivity test facilitated the acquisition of optimal τ and ω values for each site. Improvements in the SCA-V SM retrievals were assessed using metrics, including Pearson correlation coefficient (R), Root Mean Squared Difference (RMSD), Mean Difference (MEAND), and unbiased Root Mean Squared Difference (ubRMSD). Each of these metrics is calculated using (5) - (8),

where x represents the model dataset and y represents a reference dataset.

$$RMSD = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (x_i - y_i)^2} \quad (5)$$

$$MEAND = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (x_i - y_i) \quad (6)$$

$$ubRMSD = \sqrt{RMSD^2 - MEAND^2} \quad (7)$$

$$R = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N (x_i - \bar{x})(y_i - \bar{y})}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^N (x_i - \bar{x})^2 \sum_{i=1}^N (y_i - \bar{y})^2}} \quad (8)$$

III. RESULTS

A. SMAP SCA-V and DCA retrieved SM

Fig. 3 presents the SM time series derived from the SMAP SCA-V and DCA algorithms for three study sites from May 28, 2018, to September 13, 2021. Regardless of the season, SMAP SM for all sites often reach saturation (> 0.6), especially at Tambopata and Caxiuana. At the Manaus site, SMAP SM remains high (> 0.35) and shows minimal seasonal fluctuation (~ 0.15). Both SCA-V and DCA algorithms reveal similar seasonal SM trends, although DCA tends to overestimate SM more than SCA-V.

B. SMAP soil moisture and rainfall

Fig. 4 shows a subtle seasonal variation in SMAP SM and rainfall across the Amazon. The SMAP SM values during both the wet (DJF) and dry (JJA) seasons display low variability (the maximum difference being less than $0.05 m^3/m^3$). In contrast, precipitation exhibits a stark distinction between the dry and wet seasons. During the wet season (DJF), precipitation across the entire Amazon rainforest region exceeds 150 mm per month, barring the northern parts. Conversely, during the dry season (JJA), precipitation drops below 100 mm per month across most of the southern Amazon. Thus, the SMAP SCA-V SM retrievals for the Amazon rainforest do not follow the seasonal shifts in precipitation.

C. Brightness temperature (T_B) and Effective temperature

In addition to T_B , the effective temperature of soil and vegetation are essential inputs for SMAP SM retrievals (1).

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Fig. 5 compares SMAP ancillary data of modeled effective surface temperature and SMAP T_B observations with corresponding *in situ* observations. The magnitude and seasonal trend of the SMAP ancillary surface temperature align well with *in situ* observations, but the latter display larger fluctuations. Moreover, the T_{BV} and T_{BH} exhibits a similar trend, with minor differences in magnitude. These differences can provide insights into the extent of vegetation attenuation. DCA uses the difference to simulate SM and τ . Consequently, polarized T_B exhibiting similar trends and magnitudes are generally considered to lack significant informational content.

D. Comparison of SMAP SM to *in situ* SM

Fig. 6 compares SMAP SM data with *in situ* SM observations at various depths and times. At Tambopata (Fig. 6a), a single depth soil moisture *in situ* observation is available (5 cm). Significant differences in magnitude (>0.2) and a low correlation coefficient (0.398) are evident. SMAP SM overestimates compared to *in situ* observations, failing to capture observed seasonality. Fig. 6b compares SMAP SM with *in situ* observations at different depths (2.5, 5 cm, and 15 cm) at the Manaus site. *In situ* SM observations at 2.5 cm depth align better with SMAP SM than those at deeper depths, which is expected as SMAP primarily detects SM in the top 0-5 cm of bare soil. Despite SMAP SM exhibiting more pronounced seasonality than at Tambopata, the correlation coefficient is still low (0.143). Notably, most SMAP data points remain at saturation and overestimate SM compared to *in situ* data. Fig. 6c contrasts SMAP SM with *in situ* observations at the 20 cm depth at Caxiuana, the shallowest measurement depth available. *In situ* observations show strong seasonality with a dry season from August to December, yet SMAP SM does not capture this *in situ* SM seasonality at Caxiuana.

E. Optimization of SM Retrieval

Fig. 7 illustrates a sensitivity test on the SCA-V algorithm at each site using a single depth SM measurement (Tambopata: 5 cm, Manaus: 5 cm, Caxiuana: 20 cm). The left panels depict the retrieved SM for various τ values, and the right panels show the retrieved SM using SCA-V with different ω values. The magnitude and variability of the retrieved SM increase in correspondence with τ . The optimal τ value was identified to be 50% lower in Tambopata, 10-20% lower in Manaus, and 50% lower in Caxiuana than the default values in the SMAP (Soil Moisture Active Passive) ancillary data. The average τ value decreased from 1.24 to 0.62 in Tambopata, from 1.23 to 1.04 in Manaus, and from 1.24 to 0.62 in Caxiuana. This adjustment resulted in the closest alignment between the retrieved SM and the *in situ* observations at each respective site. Conversely, the magnitude of the retrieved SM decreases as the ω value increases. The closest agreement between SMAP retrieval and observed SM occurs with ω values of 0.10 (Tambopata), 0.08

(Manaus), and larger than 0.10 (Caxiuana) for each site.

Optimized SM retrievals are evaluated using two metrics (RMSD and MEAND). These metrics determine the optimized values of τ and ω for each site. Fig. 8 shows the optimized time series of SCA-V SM retrievals for the Tambopata, Manaus, and Caxiuana sites. Minimizing RMSD and MEAND yields similar SM retrievals, having a consistent magnitude compared to *in situ* observations. However, the MEAND-optimized retrievals exhibited more variability than those RMSD-optimized retrievals. Despite this, the optimized parameters do not entirely capture the seasonal and inter-annual SM variability.

Table 1 displays the default and optimized values of τ and ω corresponding to each evaluation metric. The RMSD-optimized parameters outperform the default parameters, although they show less improvement in ubRMSD. For all three sites (Tambopata, Manaus, and Caxiuana), the optimized τ is smaller (50%, 80%, and 50%) than the ancillary data, while the optimized ω (0.085, 0.06, and 0.11) is similar or higher than the ancillary data value (0.07), aligning with the sensitivity tests presented in Fig. 7.

VI. DISCUSSION

We observed significant differences between the SMAP Level-3 SM product and the *in situ* observations in the Amazon rainforest. Assessing the SMAP SM products against *in situ* observations in the Amazon rainforest can contribute to the improvement of the SMAP SM algorithm and enhance our understanding of climate change and impacts of extreme climate events in the Amazon rainforest and similar tropical ecosystems.

Previous literature has successfully validated SMAP SM using *in situ* observations across various land cover types [13], [17], [18], [19], [40], [43], [50]. These studies have demonstrated the robust performance of the SMAP algorithms with a low ubRMSD of less than $0.04 m^3/m^3$. However, an evident knowledge gap exists pertaining to the validation of SMAP SM products in tropical rainforests, such as Amazon rainforest, which are characterized by dense vegetation and tall trees. We anticipate that the quality of SMAP SM data for other tropical forest regions would be comparable to the findings in our analysis conducted in the Amazon rainforest.

Our analysis identified two dominant factors contributing to the biases between the SMAP SM and *in situ* observations. First, the coarse spatial resolution of the SMAP SM data, with a grid spacing of 9 km and a radiometric resolution of 33 km, may hinder the accurate representation of the complex Amazon landscape and create a significant resolution gap compared to the point scale *in situ* observations. Second, the dense and tall canopy layer of the Amazon rainforest can affect passive radiometer measurements by attenuating microwave radiation more strongly [51], [52], [53].

For instance, at the Caxiuana site, the SMAP SM consistently exhibits saturation levels around 0.6, contrasting

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with the observed seasonal fluctuations in the *in situ* SM observations (Fig. 6). This saturation is likely due to the presence of surrounding Amazon lakes and reservoirs within the grid area and the dense vegetation with an average tree height of 35 meters. The comparison of SMAP SM with *in situ* observations and precipitation data (Fig. 4) highlights the inadequacy of the SMAP SM in capturing the seasonal variability in SM and its response to precipitation, not only in Caxiuana but also across the broader Amazon rainforest.

Our analysis suggests that the current SMAP SCA-V retrieval algorithm underestimates the vegetation transmissivity of a dense canopy, which affects the SM retrieval. By optimizing vegetation-related parameters, namely τ and ω , we observed improvements in the SM retrieval from SMAP data. Lowering τ by 50% in Tambopata, 10-20% in Manaus, and 50% in Caxiuana altered both the magnitude and variability of SM, while adjusting ω by 27% in Tambopata, -14% in Manaus, and 57% in Caxiuana fine-tuned the magnitude of SM. However, it is crucial to note that these adjustments have limitations, and optimizing τ and ω alone may not be sufficient to universally improve the SMAP SM retrieval algorithm, as optimal parameters may vary across the Amazon rainforest.

Through the optimization of τ and ω , we also found that the low transmissivity of the Amazon rainforest due to the dense and thick canopy layer with high VWC results in lower T_B^{sim} . To make T_B^{sim} closer to the T_B^{obs} , the SMAP algorithm retrieves higher SM to increase surface emissivity in response to the low transmissivity. Increase in surface emissivity corresponds to an increase in SM and T_B^{sim} . This tendency can be observed in the comparison between SMAP T_B^{obs} and SMAP SM. The greater variations of T_B (Fig. 5) at Tambopata and Caxiuana than those at the Manaus site were presumably due to greater variability of *in situ* SM at Tambopata and Caxiuana. Yet, the variations of SMAP SM are greater at Manaus than at Tambopata and Caxiuana (Fig. 3), indicating how overestimated VWC in SMAP SM diminishes the variation of SMAP T_B^{obs} . Similarly, the comparison of SMAP SM with *in situ* observations and precipitation data (Fig. 4 & Fig. 6) highlights the insufficiency of the SMAP baseline SM retrieval algorithm in capturing soil moisture beneath the dense canopy layer. This underscores the need for further refinement of the algorithm and the potential integration of *in situ* data to enhance the accuracy of soil moisture estimations in regions characterized by dense forest cover.

The presumption is that L-band radiation, with a frequency of 1.41 GHz, can penetrate the leaves within forest canopies. However, the structure of the canopy, including elements such as trunks, branches, and stems, influences the microwave emissions emanating from the soil and canopy, which consequently diminishes the transmissivity [54]. Moreover, the dense canopies of tropical rainforests typically hold higher quantities of water in their stems during the dry seasons, which is essential for transpiration [33], [55]. As such, it is imperative for future research to incorporate additional parameters beyond τ and ω in the forward modeling of T_B ,

including considerations such as the vegetation type, structural characteristics, and water dynamics. This enhancement would facilitate more precise retrievals of SM using SMAP data, contributing to the accuracy and utility of remote sensing in hydrological and environmental studies.

However, it is important to acknowledge the limitations of this study, including the limited number of *in situ* observations and the scale gap between the *in situ* and SMAP data. The limited *in situ* observation and associated their time series makes it difficult to analyze the interannual variability of SM. Even though this analysis uses single point-scale *in situ* SM observations at each site, the biases of the SMAP SM retrievals are arguably representative of the Amazon region since the SMAP SM have substantial biases at all Amazon sites with *in situ* observations. Colliander et al. [17] highlighted the need for spatially distributed observations from multiple sensors to accurately represent SM at a 9 km resolution. Single-point observations may be biased compared to the area average and may not represent the spatial distribution of SM over the study domain. Therefore, it is desirable to use multiple sensors to validate and further improve the SM retrievals. Despite the inherent limitations associated with analyses based on single-point *in situ* observations, our study suggests that the temporal variations of SM at a single point offer valuable insights into the temporal variations of SMAP SM, thereby enhancing the understanding of remotely sensed SM dynamics [17].

V. CONCLUSIONS

This study is the first assessment of the SMAP SM for the Amazon rainforest using *in situ* observations. Comparison between the current SMAP SM and *in situ* observations showed substantial differences in all three study areas. Our findings suggest that SM retrieval algorithms need to improve for tropical rainforest areas with dense and tall vegetation. The current SMAP SCA-V algorithm overestimates SM for the Amazon region due to high VWC.

Improvement of the SMAP SM retrievals for the Amazon rainforest region may be achieved by optimizing two key parameters of the SCA-V algorithm, τ and ω . Lowering the value of the SMAP default τ can significantly reduce biases of the SCA-V SM retrievals to be consistent with *in situ* observations. In densely vegetated area, overestimated τ make the SMAP SCA algorithm retrieve SM higher as an offset. It is important to ensure that τ and ω are adjusted within reasonable ranges.

For more accurate SMAP SM retrieval in the Amazon rainforest region, considering additional canopy-related parameters is crucial. This includes factors like vegetation type, structure, and water dynamics, which impact the estimation of VWC. Although optimizing τ and ω parameters significantly reduces bias, this approach is constrained due to the limited availability of *in situ* SM observations. To enhance the SMAP SM retrievals across the entirety of the Amazon region, a novel approach not relying on *in situ* observations is needed.

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Figure 1. Study sites in the Amazon rainforest (Yellow dots). The green line denotes the boundary of the Amazon rainforest. The figure was generated by ArcGIS Pro Version 3.0.0.

82x86mm (96 x 96 DPI)

Figure 2. Diagram of the τ - ω model with canopy layer (illustrated in green). The brightness temperature (T_B) is represented as the summation of the radiative energy originating from the soil surface (depicted by the yellow line) and the contribution modified by the overlying canopy layer

89x70mm (96 x 96 DPI)

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Figure 3. Time series of SMAP SM retrieved by SMAP Single Channel Algorithm (SCA, left column) with vertically polarized brightness temperature (T_{BV}) and Dual Channel Algorithm (DCA, right column) for the grids covering the study sites. Locations of Tambopata, Manaus, and Caxiuana are shown in Figure 1

196x96mm (96 x 96 DPI)

Figure 4. Seasonal variation of SMAP SM and precipitation(P) over the Amazon rainforest region. From the top left, SM and P of the wet season (December to February, DJF), dry season (June to August, JJA), and the difference between the wet and dry seasons

101x53mm (96 x 96 DPI)

Figure 5. Time series of in situ observations (Obs.) and SMAP measured (SMAP) temperatures including surface temperature (Surface), T_{BV} (Brighness-V), and T_{BH} (Brighness-H) for sites (a) Tambopata, (b) Manaus, and (c) Caxiuana. The in situ observations of air and soil surface temperatures are employed as a reference of effective temperature inputs for the SCA SM retrieval

91x117mm (300 x 300 DPI)

Figure 6. Comparison between SMAP SM (SMAP) and in situ SM (Obs.). Tambopata site (a) has a single depth (5 cm), Manaus site (b) has multiple depths (2.5, 5, and 15 cm), and Caxiuana site (c) has a single depth (20 cm).

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Figure 7. Sensitivity test result of two τ - ω model parameters (τ : left column, ω : right column) to the SM retrieval at the Tambopata (a), Manaus (b), and Caxiuana (c) site

151x111mm (300 x 300 DPI)

Figure 8. SM retrieval at the Tambopata (a), Manaus (b), and Caxiuana (c) sites using optimized SCA-V algorithm for different evaluation metrics (RMSD and MEAND)

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time	τ	ω	RMSD (m³/m³)	MEAND (m³/m³)	ubRMSD (m³/m³)
Tambopata	τ (default)	0.07 (default)	0.31	0.30	0.06
	$\tau^*0.5$	0.085	0.05	< 0.01	0.05
Manaus	τ (default)	0.07 (default)	0.13	0.11	0.08
	$\tau^*0.8$	0.06	0.07	< 0.01	0.07
Caxiuana	τ (default)	0.07 (default)	0.23	0.23	0.05
	$\tau^*0.5$	0.11	0.07	0.06	0.06

Table 1. SM retrieval result of Tambopata, Manaus, and Caxiuana sites using optimized SMAP SCA-V algorithm for different evaluation metrics

159x62mm (300 x 300 DPI)